

A Heuristic Method For Root-Finding Using Random Numbers

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Abstract

A heuristic method to find the root of the transcendental equation is proposed. For this purpose, an intuitive approach combined with random numbers is adopted. The method is suited for a general equation $f(x) = 0$.

Keywords: Transcendental Equation, Random Numbers, Intermediate Value Property

1 Introduction

The problem of finding root of the transcendental equation

$$f(x) = 0 \tag{1}$$

has constantly attracted human endeavour all through the ages. Thus we have found new, improved methods, more accurate, more efficient, speedier than the ones before. The Mathematicians over the time have always based such method on a sound mathematical reasoning and rigorous proofs. One of the finest and simplest property in enclosing the root is the Intermediate Value Property (IVP). This leads to another simple, elegant and certain method, namely, Bisection Method to find the root of the equation (1). Despite its tortoise-like convergence, this method can be used to get close to the root as much accurate as it is desired.

With the advent of new technologies, especially computers, newer branches of Mathematics and allied areas have emerged. A few theoretical concept can now be tested and implemented with greater ease and speed. The computational power of Mathematics have grown tremendously and gave rise to, for example, a computer based proof of four colour problem which was otherwise not possible.

Random numbers have occupied an important position since its introduction in early part of the last century. Since then random numbers have been used in the computational sciences. It is well-known that a true random number is not generated by any algorithm. Instead a pseudo random numbers is obtained using the best available algorithms.

For the present work we have used (pseudo) random numbers as generated in the mathematical software MAXIMA.

2 Method

3.1 Single Root

We have combined the IVP with the power of the random number to enclose the root of the equation (1). First we assume that an enclosing interval (a, b) is known. We may then generate a single random number x between a and b and test for the sign of the function at this random number x . Applying the intermediate value property to choose the next enclosing interval and continue to repeatedly generate random numbers one after the other until a desired accuracy is achieved.

On the other hand, we may simultaneously generate two random numbers x & y ($x < y$) inside the given enclosing interval and again applying intermediate value property to obtain next enclosing interval as (a, x) or (y, b) or (x, y) . This would approximate the root speedily than the algorithm

with one random number trivially. This is implemented as a MAXIMA program on the Equation 4.1 and the results are presented in section (4).

3.2 Double Root

Like the intuitive approach to obtain single root of the equation (1), there exists a few intuitive ways to get close to the double root. Here again, we may use either one random number or two random numbers or even three random numbers at each step. The one chosen below may not be the best but it works satisfactorily and the simplest in its understanding.

We generate two random numbers x & y ($x < y$) in the given interval and a third number z is chosen as the mid-point of these two random numbers. We select the next interval using the criterion based upon the minimum of the modulus of the value of the function at these three numbers. Hence, we get the interval at the next step: (a, x) or (y, b) or (x, y) according as the minimum is at $|f(x)|$, $|f(y)|$ or $|f(z)|$. This is implemented on the Equation 4.2 using the Algorithm (A) given in section 3 and the results are presented in section (4).

3.3 General Equation $f(x)=0$

The beauty of the random numbers is that the intuitive method as presented in Algorithm (A) is able to generate all the roots in the given interval. It does not distinguish between a single root or a double roots and it does not even need the IVP at all. This has been shown with the help of equations 4.3, 4.4 and 4.5 in section (4).

3 Implementation of the Method

The code for the proposed method is written in MAXIMA version 5.47.0 and is as follows:

Algorithm A

```
/* A 20 course program with 60 iterations per course is as follows*/
runs:20$
iter:60$
f(x):=27*x^4+162*x^3-180*x^2+62*x-7$
root:(a+b)/2$
/*A random number is generated on the interval (r,s) using MAXIMA's in-built function */
rn(r,s):=r+(s-r)*random(1.0)$
  for j from 1 thru runs do (
    a:-20,
    b:10,
    for i from 1 thru iter do (
      x:rn(a,b),
      y:rn(x,b),
      z:(x+y)/2,
      m:min(abs(f(x)),abs(f(y)),abs(f(z))),
/*The following if-else condition chooses the next iteration interval */
      if m=abs(f(x)) then (root:x,b:y)
        else if m=abs(f(y)) then (root:y,a:x)
          else if m=abs(f(z)) then (root:z, a:x,b:y)
    ),
    printf( true, "~2d ~15f ~15a ~%", j,root,abs(f(root)))
  )$
```

4 Computational Results

Equation 4.1: $x^3 + x^2 - 3x - 3 = 0$, $[1,2]$.

Result: The bracketing root is obtained. The number of iteration per course is 35.

Table 4.1

Course Number	Root	f(root)
1	1.7320508075695	6.09912120808076E-12
2	1.7320508075691	2.36966002375993E-12
3	1.7320508075673	1.50208734339685E-11
4	1.7320508075689	1.26121335597417E-13
5	1.7320508075691	1.70086167372573E-12
6	1.7320508075689	1.77635683940025E-15
7	1.7320508075684	4.69668748337426E-12
8	1.7320508075688	3.78364006792253E-13
9	1.7320508075832	1.35715438887018E-10
10	1.7320508075689	2.13162820728030E-14

Equation 4.2: $x^4 - 6x^3 + 10x^2 - 6x + 9 = 0$, $[-10,10]$.

Result: A double root (3.0) is obtained while the two other roots are imaginary. The number of iteration per course is 50. Nonetheless, some false roots may also appear which can easily be eliminated by reading |f(root)|.

Table 4.2

Course Number	Root	f(root)
1	3.00000006289420	2.48689957516035E-14
2	3.00000008501720	6.03961325396085E-14
3	2.99999831718720	2.83293388747551E-11
4	3.00000003604780	3.55271367880050E-15
5	3.00000005385900	2.84217094304040E-14
6	2.99999877907840	1.49142920236045E-11
7	0.49999998044502	7.81250000000000E+00
8	3.00000250316380	6.26698692940408E-11
9	2.99999970007260	8.77520278663723E-13
10	3.00000004018690	7.10542735760100E-15

Equation 4.3: $5x^4 - 11x^2 + 2 = 0$, $[-20,15]$.

Result: All the four roots are obtained. The number of iteration per course is 60. Nonetheless, some false roots may also appear which can easily be eliminated.

Table 4.3

Course Number	Root	f(root)
1	-0.4472135933359	1.74201140179519E-08
2	1.4142135623362	9.38332078703752E-10
3	-0.4472135908154	3.77097262305170E-08
4	1.4142137325904	4.33302563251913E-06
5	1.4142135668298	1.13448230365520E-07
6	0.4472135978321	1.87730329059832E-08
7	-1.4142135466900	3.99218940572154E-07
8	-0.4472135886245	5.53463090913197E-08
9	-0.4472135917263	3.03775911092429E-08
10	0.3598555408460	6.59389970335932E-01
11	1.4142135363191	6.63225911523568E-07
12	1.4142135663078	1.00161262395204E-07
13	0.4472135954073	7.46151362918112E-10
14	0.4472186782355	4.09153613780688E-05
15	0.4472136911311	7.69815748924429E-07
16	-0.4472138405872	1.97291438519542E-06
17	1.4142135625887	5.48856959881050E-09
18	-0.4472135960077	4.08731404277773E-09
19	-1.4142135625680	4.95952079404560E-09
20	0.4472135955000	3.85469434149854E-13

Equation 4.4: $\frac{x}{1+x^2} - \frac{500}{841} \left(1 - \frac{21x}{125}\right) = 0$, $[-10,10]$.

Result: Both roots (root= 2.5 with multiplicity 2) are obtained. The number of iteration per course is 60. Nonetheless, some false roots may also appear.

Table 4.4

Course Number	Root	f(root)
1	2.5000000320874	0.0
2	2.5000000062732	0.0
3	2.4999999310656	1.11022302462515E-16
4	2.5000000799664	1.11022302462515E-16
5	2.4999996458048	2.66453525910037E-15
6	2.5000003701295	2.94209101525666E-15
7	-2.5000001007280	1.18906064209274E+00
8	2.4999999667662	0.00000000000000E+00
9	2.5000002157554	9.99200722162640E-16
10	2.5000002678993	1.55431223447521E-15
11	0.9523809544388	2.58144949860650E-10
12	2.5000000273860	0.00000000000000E+00
13	2.4999969188809	2.02449168540397E-13
14	2.5000000198887	0.00000000000000E+00
15	2.5000000584151	5.55111512312578E-17
16	2.4999999430982	0.00000000000000E+00
17	2.5000000567653	0.00000000000000E+00
18	2.5000000440491	0.00000000000000E+00
19	-1.0438833885010	1.19833376187532E+00
20	2.5000000529746	5.55111512312578E-17

Equation 4.5: $27x^4 + 162x^3 - 180x^2 + 62x - 7 = 0$, $[-20,10]$.

Result: Both roots (root=1/3 with multiplicity 3) are obtained. The number of iteration per course is 60. Nonetheless, some false roots may also appear.

Table 4.5

Course Number	Root	f(root)
1	-7.000000000705	7.51055858927429E-06
2	0.333337529381	1.24344978758017E-14
3	0.333334681770	0.00000000000000E+00
4	0.333332208730	0.00000000000000E+00
5	-6.999999999862	1.47097546232544E-06
6	0.333333796401	0.00000000000000E+00
7	0.333331043507	3.55271367880050E-15
8	0.333332198739	0.00000000000000E+00
9	0.333335003335	0.00000000000000E+00
10	0.333331442953	0.00000000000000E+00
11	0.333335475279	1.77635683940025E-15
12	0.333337811087	1.59872115546022E-14
13	-4.675994685335	7.88749857452741E+03
14	0.333334289954	1.77635683940025E-15
15	0.333335575092	3.55271367880050E-15
16	-6.999999999998	1.60102899826597E-08
17	0.333335310578	0.00000000000000E+00
19	0.333334201527	0.00000000000000E+00
20	0.333332529378	0.00000000000000E+00

It may be noted that all the computation are done on an i5 fifth Generation Intel Mac with macOS Ventura 13.7.5

5 Conclusion

In this age of Artificial Intelligence, a heuristic approach may be in tune with the times and a mathematical rigour is not always pursued with passion and this type of solution seeking approach is not only easily comprehended but also implemented with much ease. It may also be noted that the proposed method is quite stable and a mathematical analysis for the stability may present in itself another problem which needs further investigation. Finally it would not be wrong to conclude that, like the Bisection method, this methods builds its academic merits on its own.

References

1. Atkinson, Kendall E. (1989), An introduction to Numerical Analysis